

(Amberlite IR 120) column and then titrating the eluate with 0.05N NaOH. The measured values agree well with the theoretical values.

The isolation and characterisation of other salts of the complex cations, optical resolution and chromatographic studies on the complexes are in progress. The syntheses of mixed-ligand complexes using other OO, ON and NN donor ligands are progressing and details will be reported in due course.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the University Grants Commission, New Delhi-1 for financial assistance.

References

1. S. CHAN and O. W. LAN, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1969, **22**, 1869; D. A. BUCKINGHAM, D. M. FOSTER and A. M. SARGESON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 4102; K. SHUJI and M. SHIBATA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1971, **44**, 2424; K. IGI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1971, **44**, 426; M. TAKEUCHI and M. SHIBATA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1974, **47**, 2797; P. HARRIGAN, R. A. CANELLI, J. R. KASHMANN, C. A. HOFFMANN, R. BAUER, D. R. BOSTON and J. C. BAILAR, JR., *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, **13**, 1108; H. E. TOMA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 785.
2. J. C. BAILAR, JR. and J. B. WORK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 232.
3. K. YOSHIBIRO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1975, **48**, 2033.
4. M. M. JONES, *Elementary Coordination Chemistry*, Prentice Hall, 1964, p. 254.
5. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, *Advanced Inorganic Chemistry*, Second Edition, Wiley Eastern Pvt. Ltd., 1966, p. 874.

Complexes of Chromyl Chloride

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Manuscript received 22 September 1977, revised 15 February 1978, accepted 10 April 1978

CHROMYL chloride is reported to form complexes with phosphorous halides¹, amides² and titanium tetrachloride³. However, its complexes with nitrogen bases (except with pyridine⁴) have not been studied so far. The pyridine complex has also not been studied in details except the elemental analysis. The formation of complexes of chromyl chloride with nitrogen bases and some oxy-donors is being reported here.

Experimental

Chromyl chloride was prepared by the method reported by Hein and Herzog⁵. It was then repeatedly distilled and the fraction distilling at 117°/740 mm was collected.

The nitrogen bases were purified by refluxing over potassium hydroxide and were fractionally distilled. Acetylacetone and acetoacetic acid were purified by fractional distillation.

Complex Formation: Ice-cold solution of chromyl chloride in carbon tetrachloride was added dropwise to excess of ice-cold solution of the base in carbon tetrachloride. Solid product so obtained was filtered, repeatedly washed with carbon tetrachloride and dried in vacuum.

Chromium in the complexes was estimated by heating the complex to 1000-1200° and weighing the residue as Cr₂O₃. Chloride was estimated by Volhard's method.

Conductances of the complexes in N, N-dimethyl formamide were measured in a dip type cell using Toshniwal CLO1/O1 conductometer.

Infrared spectra of chromyl chloride and its complexes (as nujol mulls) were scanned on Perkin Elmer 621, double beam grating spectrophotometer using polythene plates. The mulls were prepared in a dry box.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis (Table 1) of the complexes reveals that all the adducts of nitrogen bases with chromyl chloride bear 2 : 1 stoichiometry whereas those of oxydonors (acetylacetone and acetoacetic acid bear 1 : 1 stoichiometry to chromyl chloride. All the complexes are solids at room temperature, sensitive to traces of moisture and stable only in dry atmosphere. The complexes are insoluble in most of the common organic solvents except in N,N-dimethyl formamide in which they exhibit low solubility. The molecular weights of the complexes could not be determined due to their insolubility in the solvents having convenient freezing points.

Molar conductance data of the complexes in N,N-dimethyl formamide (Table 1) reveal that all the complexes are non-ionic in nature.

TABLE-1
PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES OF CHROMYL CHLORIDE

Complex	Colour	m.p.(°C)	Molar conductance (Ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹)	% of Cr		% of Cl	
				Found	Calculated	Found	Calculated
CrO ₂ Cl ₂ .2C ₂ H ₅ N	Dark brown	159	8	16.2	16.6	22.5	22.7
CrO ₂ Cl ₂ .2C ₂ H ₅ N	Light brown	Decomposes	6	15.8	16.0	22.2	21.9
CrO ₂ Cl ₂ .2C ₂ H ₅ N	Reddish brown	165	9	12.7	12.6	17.0	17.2
CrO ₂ Cl ₂ .2C ₂ H ₅ N	Brown	Above 350	5	12.8	13.1	17.7	17.9
CrO ₂ Cl ₂ .C ₄ H ₈ O ₂	Greenish brown	—do—	4	19.9	20.4	27.9	27.8
CrO ₂ Cl ₂ .C ₄ H ₈ O ₂	Light brown	—do—	5	20.3	20.2	27.8	27.6

